

STUDY OF HUMORAL FACTORS OF ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION: ENDOTHELIN I, ANGIOTENSIN II, AND VON WILLEBRAND FACTOR IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC HEART FAILURE WHO HAVE HAD COVID-19

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ABSTRACT

During the COVID-19 pandemic, mortality rates in patients with chronic heart failure (CHF) who were infected significantly increased compared to uninfected CHF patients [1]. In the early stages of the disease, the use of sensitive methods such as immunoassay, in addition to traditional clinical and laboratory methods, is an urgent task for the early detection of clinical signs of the disease [2].

Chronic heart failure (CHF) and COVID-19 are conditions that increase the risk of endothelial dysfunction and thrombotic complications [3]. The study of Endothelin I, Angiotensin II, and Von Willebrand Factor in CHF patients who have had COVID-19 is of great importance for the early detection of cardiovascular diseases and the prevention of ensuing complications in the post-COVID period [4].

Relevance of the Study. During the COVID-19 pandemic, mortality rates in patients with chronic heart failure (CHF) who were infected significantly increased compared to uninfected CHF patients [1]. In the early stages of the disease, the use of sensitive methods such as immunoassay, in addition to traditional clinical and laboratory methods, is an urgent task for the early detection of clinical signs of the disease [2].

Chronic heart failure (CHF) and COVID-19 are conditions that increase the risk of endothelial dysfunction and thrombotic complications [3]. The study of Endothelin I, Angiotensin II, and Von Willebrand Factor in CHF patients who have had COVID-19 is of great importance for the early detection of cardiovascular diseases and the prevention of ensuing complications in the post-COVID period [4].

Objective of the Study. To study the humoral factors of endothelial dysfunction – Endothelin I, Angiotensin II, and Von Willebrand Factor – in CHF patients who have had COVID-19.

Materials and Methods. 140 patients who had recovered from COVID-19 were examined. Patients were enrolled in the study 3-5 months after contracting COVID-19. The average age of the patients was 60.92 ± 0.54 years. The following tests were performed: levels

of Endothelin I, Angiotensin II, and Von Willebrand Factor were determined by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) (Elabscience, USA).

Results. According to the analysis results, arterial hypertension was identified in all CHF patients who had had COVID-19. A diagnosis of coronary heart disease (CHD) was established in 52 (52%) of the examined patients. Among these, 30 patients had Functional Class (FC) II (30%) and 22 patients (22%) had FC III.

Endothelin I, one of the biomarkers of endothelial dysfunction, was 5.6 pg/ml in CHF patients without a history of COVID-19, and 9.13 pg/ml ($p<0.01$) in patients who had had COVID-19. The distribution of Endothelin I levels by FC in CHF patients who had had COVID-19 was as follows: 5.82 pg/ml in FC I patients, 8.76 pg/ml in FC II patients, and 11.82 pg/ml in FC III patients ($p<0.001$).

Another biomarker, Angiotensin II, was 67.95 pg/ml in CHF patients without a history of COVID-19, and 80.3 pg/ml ($p<0.01$) in patients who had had COVID-19. The distribution of Angiotensin II levels by FC in CHF patients who had had COVID-19 was as follows: 60.23 pg/ml in FC I patients, 74.63 pg/ml in FC II patients, and 100.31 pg/ml in FC III patients ($p<0.01$).

When studying the level of Von Willebrand Factor, another biomarker, its level was 1.49 U/ml in CHF patients without a history of COVID-19, and 2.15 U/ml ($p<0.001$) in patients who had had COVID-19. The distribution of Von Willebrand Factor levels by FC in CHF patients who had had COVID-19 was as follows: 1.52 U/ml in FC I patients, 2.02 U/ml in FC II patients, and 2.72 U/ml in FC III patients ($p<0.01$).

Conclusion. The research revealed that in CHF patients who had had COVID-19, an exacerbation of endothelial dysfunction in the cardiovascular wall was observed in the post-coronavirus period (3-5 months later). This is characterized by an increase in the levels of the humoral factors of endothelial dysfunction: Endothelin I, Angiotensin II, and Von Willebrand Factor.

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